

EFFECT OF SiO_2 AND Fe_3O_4 NANOPARTICLES ON YIELD OF GOLDEN DELICIOUS APPLE VARIETY**Hashimov Kh.,***Azerbaijan State University of Economics***Aliyev B.,****Musayev M.,****Ismayilova L.,****Ahmadova H.,****Sultanova C.,***National Aerospace Agency, Institute of Ecology***Guliyeva Y.***Azerbaijan State University of Economics***Abstract**

Attempts to use nanomaterials, including nanoparticles, to increase the productivity of agricultural plants, resistance to stress factors, as mineral fertilizers, are giving real results. Nanoparticles can play an important role in plant growth stimulation and protection. Experiments show that nanoparticles can migrate from the air, soil and water to the plants and affect a number of physiological processes. The effect of nanoparticles on plants can be both positive and negative, depending on their composition, concentration, methods of application, environmental conditions and the type of plants. In this article, the accumulation of nanoparticles in the fruits of trees, the flowers and leaves of which were sprayed with SiO_2 and Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, and their effect on the number and composition of fruits were studied. Since the *Golden Delicious* type of apple tree is widely used in intensive horticulture, suitable for industrial cultivation and with high productivity, the experiments were conducted on trees of this type.

Keywords: nanoparticle, apple variety, Golden Delicious, nanotechnology, productivity.

Introduction. With the development of nanotechnology, which is determined to gain the status of technology of the 21st century, it has been possible to synthesize nanoparticles with wide practical applications and exhibiting unique properties. These nanoparticles, which are extremely small in size, very light in weight, and have a high surface area relative to their volume, can spread into the environment in various ways and strongly affect the quality of soil, water, and air, which are closely related to each other. related to human health. [1,2] Therefore, plants growing at the junction of water, air and soil will be more exposed to the effect of nanoparticles. Nanoparticles with unique properties will replace herbicides used in plant protection, which will be a new option for mineral fertilizers used in the

agricultural industry. [3] Nanoparticles have already been proven to act as potential biostimulants with positive effects on plant germination, development, growth, flowering, and productivity. Nanoparticles can also play an important role in the resistance of plants to several stress factors (salinity, drought, low temperature, radiation and chemical pollutants). The use of nanoparticles can be very beneficial for agriculture and horticulture, but at the same time, there are some risks related to their effects on the environment and plants that have not been fully studied. [4,5,6]

In the literature, the Golden Delicious variety is shown as a hybrid of the Grimes Golden and Golden Reinette varieties. It was first found at the end of the 19th century in West Virginia, USA. (Picture 1.)

Picture 1. Golden Delicious apple variety

The trees of the Golden Delicious variety are small, reaching 3 m in height. The first fruits appear 2-3 years after planting. In the first year, the fruits are weak, but in the second, the branches harvest. 2-3 apples grow at one place on the branch. At the age of 6-7, it is possible to collect up to 17 kg of fruit from one tree. Golden Delicious apple trees are long-lived. [7,8] They can live up to 30 years and bear fruit. The crown of the trees is round and dense. Apple trees need pruning every year. The leaves are oval, wrinkled, and have long tips. The shade of the leaf plate is light green. The apple tree blooms in white and pink. The branches fall down when bearing fruit. Golden Delicious is a winter apple variety. The Golden Delicious apple variety is disease and cold resistant. Harvest is the end of September. After harvesting, this variety can be stored for a long time in warehouses.

The fruit of this apple variety is medium-sized, round-conical. The stem is very long, the bark is yellow-green, sparsely mottled. The pulp of the fruit of the

Golden Delicious variety is dense, slightly sour, juicy and pleasantly fragrant. The amount of sugar in fruits is 10-13%. As the harvest approaches, apples turn golden yellow. If they grow on the sunny side, a blush appears on the surface of the apple.

This variety has some disadvantages: the trees are demanding from growing conditions and care. In regions with high humidity, apple trees suffer from powdery mildew, they are intolerant of drought, and if the temperature regime during storage is not observed, the fruits may fade. [9]

Material and methods. For two years of research work (2022-2023), an area of 40 m² has been allocated for the experiment at the Scientific Research Institute of "Fruit and Tea Cultivation" located in the Guba region (Figure 2). The field is divided into three parts, each with three trees. The distance between the trees is 140 m. I - area is called A option, II- area is called B option, and III- area is called C option.

Picture 2. Experimental field

In option A, SiO₂ (silicon dioxide) nanoparticles with a size of 20 nm are given to the trees. The nanoparticles are mixed in water and given in equal amounts to each of the three trees. [10,11]

Nanofertilizer is applied to the field twice a year: during the flowering period, 40 days after flowering.

Option B – control area; No nanoparticles are delivered to this area.

In option C, Fe₃O₄ (magnetite) nanoparticles with a size of 20-30 nm are given to the trees. The nanoparticles are mixed in water and given in equal amounts to each of the three trees.

Nanofertilizer is applied to the field twice a year: during the flowering period, 40 days after flowering. [12,13]

The scientific research work was carried out for 2 (two) years. The following analyzes were carried out:

- Nanoparticles used for research at Baku State University were passed through a sonar device.

- In terms of food safety of the product obtained as a result of the research works, it was examined at Baki State University, Azerbaijan Medical University, Institute of Radiation Problems and Scientific Research Institute of Fruit and Tea Cultivation. Samples were taken

to the Electron Microscopy laboratory located at the Department of Histology at the Azerbaijan Medical University. Samples taken from the bark and pulp of the apple plant were examined in the Electron Microscopy laboratory under an electron and light microscope. As a result of the conducted analysis, it was determined that no pathological condition was observed in the cells of the apple fruit.

- As a result of the analysis carried out by the Electron Paramagnetic resonance (EPR) method in the Electron Paramagnetic laboratory of the Institute of Radiation Problems of ETN, it was confirmed that the magnetite (Fe₃O₄) nanoparticle did not penetrate into the peel, pulp and seed of the apple fruit.

- Mechanical and chemical analysis of fruits was carried out in the Biochemical analysis laboratory at the Scientific Research Institute of Fruit and Tea Cultivation.

Conclusions and discussion. The research works were conducted in the research area located at the Institute of Fruit and Tea Cultivation in Guba region in 2022-2023. In the tables given below, the results of phenological, pomological and chemical analyzes of the Golden Delicious apple variety are shown in a comparative form. Table 1 shows the phenological observations for 2 years.

Table 1.

Phenological observations of the Golden Delicious variety for 2022-2023

Phenological observation	2022	2023
Bud awakening	13.04.2022	05.04.2023
First flowering	19.04.2022	20.04.2023
Full bloom	25.04.2022	26.04.2023
End of flowering	05.05.2022	06.05.2023
Harvesting	19.09.2022	21.09.2023

If we compare the pomological observations given in Table 2, we will see that an increase in the number and weight of the fruit was observed in 2023 compared to 2022.

Table 2.

Pomological observations on the Golden Delicious apple variety (19.09.2022/21.09.2023)

Plot no Tree no	The number of ripe fruits number		Weight of ripe fruits, kg		The size of the circumference of the fruit, cm		Fruit height, cm	
	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023
S1:A1	173	175	13.7	21.3	20	21	6	6.5
S1:A2	8	100	1.2	12.3	20	20.5	6.5	7
S1:A3	140	140	13.6	17.3	21	21	7	6.3
S2:A1	3	53	0,4	6.5	20	20	6	6.2
S2:A2	60	60	7.4	7.4	21,5	20	6.2	6
S2:A3	12	70	1,5	8.6	20	21.3	6.5	6
S3:A1	126	128	10.4	15.8	21.2	21.5	6.5	6
S3:A2	17	145	1.9	17.9	21	20.2	6.5	6.3
S3:A3	91	89	8.9	11	21	21	6.5	6.5

If we compare the mechanical and chemical analysis indicators of the fruits given in Table 3, we will see that in 2023, compared to 2022, an increase was observed in the amount of total sugar, the amount of soluble matter, and the amount of acidity.

Table 3.

Mechanical and chemical analysis indicators of fruits of apple varieties (Golden Delicious)

By wet weight, in %

№	The name of the variety	Humidity		Sugar in %						Soluble dry matter		Vitamin C, in mg %		Acidity	
				Mono-saxaridlər		Saxaroza		Cəmi							
		2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023
1	Area 1, Tree 1, Fe ₃ O ₄	84,0	83,0	9,39	10,80	1,93	0,69	11,32	11,49	14,5	15,0	2,64	2,11	0,27	0,32
2	Area 1, Tree 2, Fe ₃ O ₄	84,0	81,0	9,90	10,63	1,10	3,29	11,00	13,92	14,2	17,0	2,99	2,11	0,25	0,37
3	Area 1, Tree 3, Fe ₃ O ₄	84,0	78,0	10,54	10,84	0,84	1,04	11,38	11,84	14,0	13,4	2,99	2,99	0,23	0,48
4	Area 2, Tree 2, kontrol	85,0	73,0	9,3	11,26	1,67	3,48	10,97	14,74	13,2	17,0	2,82	2,29	0,27	0,40
5	Area 2, Tree 3, kontrol	85,0	83,0	9,65	9,65	1,93	2,88	11,58	12,53	14,2	15,5	2,64	2,11	0,27	0,37
6	Area 3, Tree 1, SiO ₂	75,0	81,0	15,09	11,16	2,23	2,53	17,32	13,69	22,0	17,5	2,11	1,94	0,45	0,33
7	Area 3, Tree 2, SiO ₂	82,0	80,0	11,88	11,97	1,84	0,16	13,72	12,13	15,6	17,0	1,76	2,29	0,30	0,40
8	Area 3, Tree 3, SiO ₂	85,0	78,0	10,88	13,07	0,17	2,67	11,05	15,74	13,5	19,5	1,76	2,11	0,27	0,48

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